

Abstract

This study was conducted as part of the evaluation of a prototype presented in the thesis "Dual-Modeling Approaches in CI/CD: An Agnostic Modeling Framework to Streamline DevOps." The evaluation involved configuring CircleCI scripts, followed by a tutorial of the platform to be tested and a task based on this tutorial. The study utilized questionnaires such as SUS and NASA-TLX to assess the usability and required task effort.

A Unified Modeling Framework for CI/CD Pipelines

Information and User Participation Consent

The experiment aims to validate and test a tool designed to speed up CI/CD pipeline configuration and migration between DevOps platforms. The tool is built on a platform-independent generic metamodel, allowing it to serve as a basis for developing platform-specific metamodels adapted to various DevOps platforms. Participants will configure CircleCI scripts and generate validated CircleCI scripts. Models, transformations and some intermediate steps are already configured, therefore no tasks will include creating new models or changing existing ones. Participants will test one approach provided by the researcher, either textual or visual, and will use similar industry tools as a comparison, such as VS Code for textual and Buddy for the visual approach. Prior knowledge of DevOps and the Eclipse environment would be useful but not mandatory to participate in this experiment.

The experiment will be conducted via a Zoom video call, with the researcher providing them with remote access and receiving a participant number assigned by the researcher at the beginning.

Participation is voluntary, with no personal or monetary benefits provided in return.

The experiment will last approximately **40 minutes** and participants will answer questions about the executed tasks through an online form. Personal data collected during the experiment is confidential and will only be used for research purposes. It will exclusively focus on tool usability evaluation, so don't mind if you make mistakes along the way. Participants are not under evaluation, our work is. Please carefully read the task instructions and feel free to ask any questions. Your feedback, whether written or spoken, about the tool during the experiment is highly encouraged during the experiment.

* Indicates a mandatory question

Demographic Questions

The form below includes questions concerning personal information for further analysis of the findings. Please read all the questions carefully before beginning the tasks.

1. Participant Number (provided by the investigator) *

2. Age *

3. Gender *

Male

Female

Prefer not to say

4. Highest Academic Degree Obtained (or on-going) *

- High School
- Bachelor's Degree
- Master's Degree
- Doctor's Degree
- Other: _____

5. Primary field of study *

- Computer Science
- Information Technology
- Engineering
- Business
- Science
- Arts/Humanities
- Other: _____

6. Current Job Title *

- Student
- Software Developer
- Software engineer
- DevOps Engineer
- IT Manager
- Systems Administrator
- Other: _____

7. How many years of experience do you have with CI/CD tools? *

- Never used
- Less than 1 year
- 1-3 years
- 4-6 years
- 7-10 years
- More than 10 years

8. How often do you use CI/CD tools in your current role? *

- Never
- Rarely
- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly

9. How would you rate your technical expertise in managing CI/CD pipelines? *

- Beginner
- Intermediate
- Advanced
- Expert

10. Would you prefer using a textual approach (e.g., JSON/YAML syntax) or a visual approach to configure CI/CD pipelines? *

- Textual approach (e.g., JSON syntax)
- Visual approach (e.g., drag-and-drop)

11. Which CI/CD tool do you primarily use? *

- CircleCI
- Jenkins
- GitLab CI/CD
- GitHub Actions
- Travis CI
- None
- Other: _____

12. In which industry do you currently work? *

- Technology/Software
- Finance
- Healthcare
- Education
- Manufacturing
- Other: _____

13. Are you familiar with the YAML syntax? *

- Yes
- No

14. Select configuration mode (provided by researcher) *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

Textual Approach

Tutorial (Estimated time: 7 min)

Let's configure the first script alongside a tutorial. To do so, follow these steps:

1. Follow the **tutorial** file in the 'CICD_DSL' project. Note that **test.circleci** will return an error because you did not complete the tutorial.
2. When you've finished configuring, right-click **test.circleci** and click on **Convert DSL to XMI** -> **Convert**. This step will convert our configuration into an XMI file.
3. Click on the arrow next to the green button and select **Generate CircleCI Script**. This will generate the final script in the 'script' folder to be validated.
4. In Powershell, copy these commands to validate the script:
 - o `cd C:\Users\alexa\.circleci`
 - o `Copy-Item -Path "D:\Eclipse\eclipse\runtime-EclipseApplication\CICD_DSL\script\script.yml" -Destination .\`
 - o `circleci config validate .\script.yml`
5. The task is successful when 'Config file at .\script.yml is valid.' appears.

Task 1 (Estimated time: 10 min)

Let's use the script from the **Tutorial** and further configure it. This time some errors will be introduced, and you'll have to resolve them. The files have already been created in the **Tutorial**, so the following steps will update them.

1. In **test.circleci**, add the following components to the configuration:
 - a. Add a Job named '**build**' that reuses "**exec**" executor and has a Run named "**Run tests**" with a RunCommand named "**yarn test**". (**Has 2 errors**)
 - b. In the new "**build**" Job you added, after "**exec**" executor add a Parameter named "**clean**" of type **BOOLEAN** and default "**2.7**" (**Has 1 error**)
 - c. In "**build-and-deploy**" Workflow, add a JobWorkflow named "preinstall". **Has 1 error**
 - d. Correct all errors you encountered and check each error message by mousing over them. Goback to step a). **HINT:** Use Quickfix feature to help correct those errors
2. Continue to configure according to **Text 2 (below)**. Note that some names and

componentschanged, so adapt according to **Text 2 (below)**.

3. When you've finished configuring, right-click **test.circleci** and click on **Convert -> ConvertDSL to XMI**. This step will convert our configuration into an XMI file.
4. Click on the arrow next to the green button and select **Generate CircleCI Script**. This will generate the final script in the 'script' folder to be validated.
5. In Powershell, copy these commands to validate the script:
 - `cd C:\Users\alexa\.circleci`
 - `Copy-Item -Path "D:\Eclipse\eclipse\runtime-EclipseApplication\CICD_DSL\script\script.yml" -Destination .\`
 - `circleci config validate .\script.yml`
6. The task is successful when 'Config file at .\script.yml is valid.' appears.

Text 2

Change the last Job name you added to **"test"** and change **"clean"** Parameter default value to **"false"**. Add a **When_Unless** with condition **"parameters.clean"** and a **when_step**. This **when_step** has a Run named **"Conditional clean up"** that runs a RunCommand named **"rm -rf node_modules"**.

In **"build"** Job add a Run named **"Build project"** with a RunCommand named **"yarn build"**.

In **"build-and-deploy"** workflow, **"test"** JobWorkflow requires **"build"** Job to run.

Part 2

VS Code Tutorial (Estimated time: 6 min)

Let's configure the first script. To do so, follow these steps:

1. Follow the **"VS Code Tutorial" (below)**
2. Once you finish the tutorial, there's a Powershell terminal in the tab below the script
3. Copy these commands to validate the script:
 - `cd C:\Users\alexa\.circleci`
 - `circleci config validate .\script.yml`

The task is successful when 'Config file at .\script.yml is valid.' appears.

VS Code Tutorial

First, specify the CircleCI configuration version as by typing: **version: 2.1**

Sections and objects are defined by stating their name followed by **:**. For every object definition, press Enter and TAB to follow the object hierarchy. You can see a Section as a list of objects.

Executors define the environment in which tasks will run. Write **executors:** to start the section. Press Enter and TAB to name the executor as **default:** . Write **docker:** to specify that **default** uses docker container and this container runs in a **circleci/node:lts** image by typing **- image:** .In the **docker:** column, write **resource_class: medium** to specify the resource allocation.

In the example above, **docker** and **resource_class: medium** are both **default** attributes, therefore a TAB is required after the **default** column to specify they are their attributes. The same logic applies to **image: circleci/node:lts**, which is a **docker** attribute.

This is the result:

```
-----  
version: 2.1  
executors:  
  default:  
    docker:  
      - image: circleci/node:lts  
      resource_class: medium  
-----
```

Now define a **jobs:** section with a job named **lint:** that uses the **default** executor by typing **executor: default** with a TAB so this executor is defined as a **lint** attribute. Define **steps:** section (list of job steps) where **lint** job has the following steps (**NOTE** that every step have **"- "** before its keyword):

1. **- checkout**
2. **- run:** named **Run ESLint** with command **npm run lint**. Since **name:** and **command:** are run attributes, give a TAB to define them

This is the result:

```
-----  
version: 2.1  
  
executors:  
  default:  
    docker:  
      - image: circleci/node:lts  
      resource_class: medium  
  
jobs:  
  lint:  
    executor: default  
    steps:  
      - checkout  
      - run:  
        name: Run ESLint  
        command: npm run lint  
-----
```

Now define a **workflows:** section to orchestrate jobs. Define a workflow named **lint_build:** then write **jobs:** to list the jobs to run and write **- lint** to include this job.

This is the result:

```
-----  
version: 2.1  
  
executors:  
  default:  
    docker:  
      - image: circleci/node:lts  
    resource_class: medium  
  
jobs:  
  lint:  
    executor: default  
    steps:  
      - checkout  
      - run:  
        name: Run ESLint  
        command: npm run lint  
  
workflows:  
  lint_build:  
    jobs:  
      - lint  
-----
```

You now finished the tutorial!

Task 1 (Estimated time: 10 min)

Let's use the script from the **Tutorial** and further configure it. This time some errors will be introduced into the task and you'll have to resolve them.

1. In VS Code add the following components to the configuration:
 - a. Before **executors:** section, write a **commands:** section to define comands so jobs can reuse them. Write a **install-dependencies:** command that has a **parameters:** section with a **include-dev:** parameter. This parameter has **type: boolean** and **default: !**. **install-dependencies** command has a **steps:** section with a **- checkout** step (**Has 1 error**)
 - b. Create a **lint:** job that uses **exec** executor and has the following steps (**Has 2 errors**):
 1. **- checkout**
 2. **- install-dependencies:** and has **include-dev:** paramater set to **false**
 3. **- run:** named **Run build script** with command **npm run build**
 - c. In **lint_build** workflow add a **- deploy** Job (**Has 1 error**)
 - d. Correct all errors you encountered in previous steps, starting at step **a**).
2. Continue to configure according to **Text 4** (below)

3. Once you finish configuring, there's a Powershell terminal in the tab below the script.
4. Copy these commands to validate the script:
 - `cd C:\Users\alexa\.circleci`
 - `circleci config validate .\script.yml`

The task is successful when 'Config file at .\script.yml is valid.' appears.

Text 4

In **install-dependencies** command, create a - **run:** step named **Install dependencies** and a command: |
`if ["<< parameters.include-dev >>" = "true"]; then`
`npm install`
`else`
`npm install --production`
`fi`

In **lint** job, add - **install-dependencies:** step with **include-dev:** as **true**.

Change the last Job name you added to **build**.

In **lint_build** workflow, change the last job name to **build** and this job requires **lint** job to run. Specify this condition with this syntax:

workflows:

jobs:

- job1

- job2:

requires:

- job1

Tasks

Visual Approach

Tutorial (Estimated time: 7 min)

In this task, you will use the Eclipse Sirius diagramming tool to configure the first script. To do so, follow these steps:

1. Follow the tutorial as shown in **Document 1**
2. When you've finished the tutorial, configure it according to **Text 5 (below)**.
3. Click on the arrow next to the green button and select **Generate CircleCI Script**. This will generate the final script in the **script** folder to be validated.
4. In Powershell, copy these commands to validate the script:

- cd C:\Users\alexa\.circleci
 - Copy-Item -Path "D:\Eclipse\eclipse\runtime-EclipseApplication\CICD_Visual\script\script.yml" -Destination .\
 - circleci config validate .\script.yml
5. The task is successful when 'Config file at .\script.yml is valid.' appears.

Text 5

In **install-dependencies** Job add these steps:

1. Checkout
2. Run Step named **Install dep** that has a Run Command named **yarn install --frozen-lockfile**

Task 1 (Estimated time: 10 min)

Let's use the script from the **Tutorial** and further configure it. This time some errors will be introduced into the task and you'll have to resolve them. The files have already been created in the **Tutorial**, so the following steps will update them.

1. Add the following components to the configuration:
 - a. Add a Command in Pipeline Tools named **attach_project** with a Parameter named **input** of type **BOOLEAN** and default **2.7**, and this Command has a Checkout Step and an Attach_workspace Step that attaches at **~/project (Has 1 error)**
 - b. Create a Job in Pipeline Tools named **lint** that reuses **exec** executor and has a Run Step named **Lint files**. **Lint files** Step has a Run Command named **yarn lint (Has 1 error)**
 - c. In **build-and-deploy** Workflow, add a JobWorkflow named **lint_test (Has 1 error)**
 - d. Correct all errors encountered in previous steps, starting in step **a)**. Check error messages by mousing over them
2. Configure it according to **Text 6 (below)**.
3. Click on the arrow next to the green button and select **Generate CircleCI Script**. This will generate the final script in the 'script' folder to be validated.
4. In Powershell, copy these commands to validate the script:
 - cd C:\Users\alexa\.circleci
 - Copy-Item -Path "D:\Eclipse\eclipse\runtime-EclipseApplication\CICD_Visual\script\script.yml" -Destination .\
 - circleci config validate .\script.yml
5. The task is successful when 'Config file at .\script.yml is valid.' appears.

Text 6

lint Job reuses **attach_project** command and add a Store Artifact Step with path **./lint-reports** and destination **lint-reports**.

In **build-and-deploy** workflow, change the last JobWorkflow name to **lint** that requires **install-dependencies** job to run

Part 2

Buddy Tutorial (Estimated time: 5 min)

Let's configure the first script. To do so, follow the tutorial as shown in **Document 2**

Task 1 (Estimated time: 10 min)

Let's use the script from the **Tutorial** and further configure it. This time some errors will be introduced into the task and you'll have to resolve them. **HINT**: you can modify the actions that are producing errors with instructions from the previous configuration.

1. In Actions tab add the following components to the configuration:
 - a. Create a Node.js command action below **create file** action that runs **npm run test** and **npm command** commands. This action is named **test (Has 1 error)**
 - b. Create a Local Shell command action named **success message** that runs **echo "Test complete"** command running in an **img** image with version **20 (Has 1 error)**. **Hint**: check **create file** action's **image**
 - c. Click on **Run new** and **Run now** to run this configuration and see logs to correct all errors you encountered. You can rerun the configuration by pressing the **Retry** button in the action that produced the error.
2. Continue to configure according to **Text 8 (below)**
3. Click on **Run new** and **Run now** to run this configuration
4. The task is successful when every action in the configuration is green.

Text 8

Drag **test** action before **build** action.

In **build** action, in **Conditions** tab, **build** action only runs if **test** action is **success**.

Change **success message** action SHELL from **Bash** to **SH** in Run tab, change container **image** to **library/docker** with **latest** version. In **Conditions** tab, **success message** action only runs if **build** action status is **success**.

Questionnaire

The following questions are asking about your experience using both tools, aiming to evaluate its effectiveness and usability. Your honest feedback on recent tasks is appreciated for identifying areas for improvement in our tool.

* Indicates a mandatory question

1. Select configuration mode (provided by researcher) *.

Textual

Visual

Textual Approach

2. How effective were the custom validators in detecting errors in your DSL code? *

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very Effective

3. How clear and understandable were the error messages provided by the custom validators? *

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very Clear

4. How useful were the quickfix suggestions in correcting the detected errors? *

1 2 3 4 5

Not Very Useful

5. How much did the quickfix features improve your efficiency in correcting errors? *

1 2 3 4 5

Grea Greatly Improved

6. How relevant did the content assist feature provide the suggestions? *

1 2 3 4 5

Very e Very Relevant

7. Did the content assist feature cover all the necessary elements and options you needed? *

1 2 3 4 5

Not r Completely Covered

8. How much did the content assist feature improve your overall efficiency and usability of the DSL? *

1 2 3 4 5

Grea Greatly Improved

Visual Approach

9. How easy was it to interact with and navigate the visual diagram in Sirius Eclipse? *

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very Easy

10. How effective was the validation feature in catching errors while configuring CI/CD pipelines? *

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very Effective

11. How clear and understandable were the validation messages provided by the tool? *

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very Clear

12. How would you rate the visual representation of the CI/CD pipeline in terms of clarity and comprehensibility? *

1 2 3 4 5

Very Excellent

13. How easy was it to fix the errors identified by the validation feature? *

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very Easy

14. How much did the validation feature help in reducing errors during the configuration process? *

1 2 3 4 5

Sign Significantly Reduced Errors

Textual Approach Open-Ended Questions

Optional questions to answer

15. What did you like most about the textual modeling approach and its features

16. What aspects of the textual modeling approach do you think could be improved?

Visual Approach Open-Ended Questions

Optional questions to answer

17. What did you find most helpful about the visual diagram and validation feature in Sirius Eclipse?

18. How can the visual diagramming tool and its validation feature be improved to better meet your needs?

System Usability Questionnaire

This section will present some statements regarding the usability of **our tool**.

19. I think that I would like to use this system frequently. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

20. I found the system unnecessarily complex. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

21. I thought the system was easy to use. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

22. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

23. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

24. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

25. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

26. I found the system very cumbersome to use. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

27. I felt very confident using the system. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

28. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

This section will present some statements regarding the usability of the **commercial tool**.

29. I think that I would like to use this system frequently. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

30. I found the system unnecessarily complex. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

31. I thought the system was easy to use. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

32. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this *
system.

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

33. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

34. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

35. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

36. I found the system very cumbersome to use. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

37. I felt very confident using the system. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

38. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system. *

1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Strongly agree

